

COMBINATION OF ADVANCEMENT FLAP AND MODIFIED LIMBERG FLAP TO CLOSE BIG CIRCULAR LATERAL FOREHEAD DEFECT

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ABSTRACT There are several options for forehead defect reconstruction; including skin grafts, different local flaps, regional flaps, and free flaps. To optimally match colour, contour and texture, the best approach replace 'like with like'. We proposed in this article the use of a combination of advancement flap and modified Limberg flap to close a big circular defect in the lateral forehead region (6cm). We divided the circular defect into two virtual circles, and then we assured the coverage for each circle separately.

KEYWORDS Advancement flap, Lateral forehead, Local flap, Limberg flap

Introduction

Reconstruction of forehead defect offers multiple challenges: First the inelasticity and slightly convex surface of the forehead skin. Second, the forehead is bounded by two critical facial landmarks that, if altered, cause an apparent visual flaw: the brow and the hairline.

Several techniques may be applied to achieve the closure of a given defect. The ideal reconstruction relies on a careful assessment of each clinical case.

Grafts or local flaps efficiently repair minor defects that do not involve exposure of vital structures. The exposure of anatomical structures such as muscles, bones, dura mater, and blood vessels require a more complex coverage, which may be performed with local or distant flap [1].

The lateral forehead region is situated between paramedian forehead region and the temple, the underlying bony curvature

goes from flat in the paramedian forehead to concave in the lateral forehead and the temple, and so the direction of rest skin tension lines in those areas is different (vertical in paramedian forehead and oblique in the lateral forehead and the temple). It seems more reasonable to use different flaps with different skin tension direction to assure the maximum coverage and the maximum sutures resistance.

We proposed in this article the use of a combination of advancement flap and modified Limberg flap to close a big circular defect (6cm) in the lateral forehead region.

The particularity of this approach is that we consider two virtual circles inside the big circular defect, and we use a different flap to close each circle.

In the first circle (medial) we use a rectangular advancement flap, for the second circle we use a Limberg modified flap. This approach can be useful each time we have a circular defect in a zone of transition between two regions which have a different direction of rest skin tension line.

Case presentation

A 68 years old woman was addressed to our department to assure the management of a basal cell carcinoma of the right lateral forehead of 1-year evolution. We first realized the tumour resection with safe margins, which left a defect of 6 cm [Fig. 1]. After receiving the histological tumour-free surgical margins proof, we scheduled the surgery. We drew the pattern of our

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Fig.1. Defect after tumour-free margins excision.

reconstruction. The first line presents the diameter of our circular defect (D), in each half of the circle we count a distance equal to the $\frac{1}{4}$ of the radius than we drew two others line (D1, D2), four segments are obtained. The coverage of the two medial segments was assured by an advancement flap, where the coverage of the two lateral segments was assured by modified Limberg flap (Quaba and Sommerlad), this flap was planned by extending out the line D2 by about two-thirds of its length (AX) and then taking a line drawn at 60° , almost parallel to the side of the defect.

Theoretically, the big circular defect was divided into two virtual circles, D1 present the diameter of the medial circle and D2 the diameter of the lateral circle. [Fig. 2] [Fig. 3].

Fig.2. Diagram showing the plan of our reconstruction on the patient.

The two flaps were designed with careful consideration of the final location of resulting scars, to best camouflage within natural rest lines. The plane of dissection was carried out superficial to the frontalis muscle and deep to the subcutaneous tissue.

Fig.3. Diagram showing the plan of our reconstruction.

Fig.4. The resulting suture line after reconstruction.

Fig.5. The aspect after reconstruction showing preservation the symmetry of brow and hairlines.

Care was taken while flap remaining to preserve the frontal branch of the facial nerve. The closure of the defect was assured without tension. To prevent any fluid collection under the flaps, we put a small drainage tube. The dressing was changed three times a week. The postoperative period was uneventful for the patient, with a good wound healing [Fig. 4] [Fig. 5]. The patient was followed up clinically for one year, each side of the forehead was symmetric, and the scars were hidden in the skin wrinkles.

Discussion

The forehead defects are often caused by tumour resection, the 3 main goals of forehead defect reconstruction are [2]:

1. Preservation of motor function and if possible sensory nerve function.
2. Maintenance of the normal boundaries of the forehead temporal aesthetic unit, including the position and symmetry of the brow, as well as temporal and frontal hairlines.
3. Optimal scar camouflage by placement of scars in relaxed tension lines or adjacent to the hairline or brow whenever is possible.

The lateral forehead is a concave area which begins at the midbrow and extends to the lateral brow where it joins the upper temple.

Multiple options were proposed to cover the lateral forehead defect, these techniques include, secondary healing, primary closure, grafts and local as well as distant flaps.

When the defect results from excision of a tumour with a significant chance of recurrence it may be best managed by second intention healing [2]. From an aesthetic standpoint, a relatively small superficial wound in a concave anatomical area is considered ideal for secondary intention healing [3].

However, in the large wound of the forehead, the eyebrows and scalp line may become displaced with secondary intention healing [2].

When the size of the defect is smaller than 3 cm, the primary closure can present a suitable solution [4], the forehead aesthetic unit border, including hairline and brow, may be used to hide incisions for improved scar camouflage [2].

Skin graft offers adequate coverage of a large defect when the wound is allowed to granulate [5], but provides a poor match in thicknesses and colour [6,7] and should be considered a temporary measure [5].

Local flaps provided like tissue for reconstruction [8] but had previously been limited to smaller defects in this region and suboptimal scarring [9,10]. The forehead is one of the facial units where advancement flap is often applied; transposition flap may be designed to move glabellar or temporal skin into the defect [2].

In some instances, tissue expansion of adjacent forehead provides adequate coverage, but it requires two stages.

Free tissue transfer has been used successfully for forehead defect approaching 50 %, or when the adjacent tissues are compromised [4]. But the Long duration of the surgery, with high surgical-anaesthetic risk, and comorbidities may affect the success of the technique in the older adults.

The lateral forehead is flattered smoothly blending into the more concave temporal region, while the paramedian forehead tends to be convex [2]. The rest skin tension lines are vertical in paramedian forehead and oblique in the temple. The skin in the temporal area is extremely mobile because of its loose attachments to the underlying temporalis fascia, and it may act as a tissue reservoir for reconstruction [2], taking all those elements in considerations, we assured the closure of a big defect in the lateral forehead (6cm) using the combination of two local flaps movements, advancement flap medial to the defect and transposition modified Limberg flap described by Quaba and Sommerlad [11], to assure a good coverage with a tension-free closure. This technique facilitates the use of local flaps in the Reconstruction of large lateral forehead defects and provides excellent aesthetic results. Dividing a big circular defect into two virtual circles and assure the reconstruction of each circle separately can be useful each time we face a defect situated between 2 zones with different tension line orientation.

Conclusion

The combination of two local flaps with different movements can offer a wide range of solution to close the big circular forehead defect.

Author contributions

Sabur Sarah wrote this article. All authors have read and agreed to the final version of this manuscript and have equally contributed to its content and the management of the cases.

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Competing Interests

Written informed consent obtained from the patients for publication of this article and any accompanying images

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